

Quantitative relationship of diamagnetic susceptibility with molecular connectivity and van der Waals volume in carboxylic acids

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A quantitative analysis is made on the relationship of diamagnetic susceptibility of carboxylic acids with Kier's molecular connectivity index (${}^1\chi_v$) and van der Waals volume (V_w). The regression analysis reveals a significant linear correlation of diamagnetic susceptibility with ${}^1\chi_v$ and V_w .

The molecular connectivity index (${}^1\chi_v$) which simply signifies the degree of branching or connectivity in a molecule and which is derived from the numerical extent of branching or connectivity in the molecular skeleton was proposed by Randic¹. The connectivity index can be correlated with several physical and chemical properties of molecules². The molecular connectivity has several versions. The simplest as well as extended versions of it all are calculated from a hydrogen suppressed graph of the molecule, designated as first order valence connectivity (${}^1\chi_v$),

$${}^1\chi_v = \sum (\delta_i^v \delta_j^v)^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

Here the sum is the overall connections or edges in such a graph and δ_i^v and δ_j^v are numbers assigned to each atom reflecting the number of atoms adjacent or connected to atom (i) and (j) which are formally bonded. The atom connectivity term (δ_i^v) is defined as

$$\delta_i^v = \frac{Z_i^v - h_i}{Z - Z_i^v - 1} \quad (2)$$

where Z_i^v is number of valence electrons of atom (i), Z the atomic number of atom (i) and h_i the number of hydrogen atoms attached to atom (i). Another parameter accounting for the size of a molecule, van der Waals volume (V_w) has also been used for correlation with diamagnetic susceptibility. V_w is calculated by assuming spherical shapes for all atoms in accordance with Bondi³. Since van der Waals radii are greater than covalent radii, the necessary corrections for overlap of atomic orbitals, and for branching in hydrocarbon chains are also taken from literature⁴.

The diamagnetic susceptibility depends upon the specific orientation of atoms in a molecule and the electronic environment generated. It is generally known that the diamagnetic susceptibility for many organic compounds may be predicted theoretically by considering it more or less additive⁵. Various semi-empirical theories

have been given for the calculation of diamagnetic susceptibilities of organic compounds. But the best theory was proposed by Pascal⁶. According to this theory molecular susceptibility of an organic compound is represented as

$$\chi_M = \sum n_A \chi_A \quad (3)$$

where the summation is to be performed over all atomic species in the molecule, n_A is the number of atoms of susceptibility χ_A in the molecule. Although Pascal's theory is very successful for a large number of organic compounds, but it does not count the effect of variation in bonding. The susceptibility of a doubly bonded oxygen atom (e.g. in an aldehyde) is quite different from contribution of a singly bound oxygen (e.g. in an alcohol). Another shortcoming of this method is that it cannot account for the difference in susceptibility between different isomers. So, Pascal accounts for these variations by replacing equation (3) by equation (4),

$$\chi_M = \sum n_A \chi_A + \sum \alpha \quad (4)$$

where α is a correction depending on the nature of the bond between atoms. In our previous work^{7,8}, we have established a quantitative relationship of diamagnetic susceptibility with molecular connectivity in hydrocarbons and alcohols. Now attempt has been made to correlate diamagnetic susceptibility with molecular connectivity and van der Waals volume in carboxylic acid series, because both the parameters account for the degree of branching, connections and size of the molecules.

Results and Discussion

The molecular connectivity and van der Waals volume calculated for some carboxylic acids as described in literature, are listed in Table 1. The diamagnetic susceptibility values are taken from literature⁹⁻³⁶.

The level of significance of this linear relationship of diamagnetic susceptibility (χ_M) with molecular connec-

Note

tivity (${}^1\chi_v$) and van der Waals volume (V_w) are shown by equations (5) and (6),

$$\chi_M = 23.030 {}^1\chi_v (\pm 0.342) + 10.185 \quad (5)$$

$$N = 40, r = 0.9958, s = 3.432, F(1,38) = 4532.957$$

$$\chi_M = 74.9232 V_w (\pm 1.6154) - 8.507 \quad (6)$$

$$N = 40, r = 0.9913, s = 4.9598, F(1,38) = 2150.98$$

In regression analysis, the statistical parameters, (N) the number of data points, (r) the correlation coefficient, (s) the standard deviation and (F) the ratio between the variance of calculated and observed data, exhibit very high level of significance of the correlation. The diamagnetic susceptibility values calculated from equations

Table 1. Diamagnetic susceptibilities of some carboxylic acids calculated by molecular connectivity (${}^1\chi_v$) and van der Waals volume (V_w)

Compounds	${}^1\chi_v$	V_w	χ_M		Ref.
			Exp.	Cal. (Eqn. 5) (Eqn. 6)	
Methanoic acid	0.493	0.347	19.9	21.539 17.491	9
Ethanoic acid	0.927	0.501	31.8	31.535 29.029	10
Propanoic acid	1.487	0.655	43.44 ^a 43.5	44.432 40.568	11 9
Butanoic acid	1.987	0.809	55.10 ^a 55.07	55.947 52.106	9 13
2-Methylpropanoic acid	1.869	0.759	56.06 ^a 59.9	53.23 48.36	15 6
Pentanoic acid	2.487	0.963	66.85 ^a 65.5	67.463 63.644	12 11
3-Methylbutanoic acid	2.342	0.913	67.7	64.123 59.898	14
Hexanoic acid	2.987	1.117	77.92 ^a 78.55	78.987 75.182	11 16
Heptanoic acid	3.487	1.271	89.3 89.74 ^a	90.493 86.72	11 12
Octanoic acid	3.987	1.425	99.5	102.009 98.258	16
Stearic acid	8.987	2.965	220.8	217.162 215.64	25
Oleic acid	8.663	2.923	209.6	209.7 210.493	13
Oxalic acid	0.854	0.59	34.07	29.853 35.698	36
Malonic acid	1.56	0.744	46.3	46.113 47.236	20
Succinic acid	2.06	0.898	57.92	57.628 58.774	20
Fumaric acid	1.763	0.858	49.11	50.768 55.779	21
Maleic acid	1.763	0.858	49.68	50.388 55.777	22
2-Methylmalonic acid	2.218	1.01	57.85	61.267 67.165	21
Glycine	1.188	0.638	40.3 ^a 39.0	37.546 39.294	19 18
Alanine	1.895	0.754	48.9	53.828 47.985	18
2-Aminobutanoic acid	2.163	0.908	61.8 ^a 61.7	60.001 59.235	18 17
2-Aminopentanoic acid	2.66	1.062	69.5 ^a 69.38	71.447 71.001	18 17
Glutamic acid	2.736	1.161	73.85 ^a 73.4	73.197 78.497	19 18
DL-Valine	2.535	1.012	71.0 ^a 70.96	68.568 67.315	18 17
Tartaric acid	2.279	0.984	69.1	67.672 65.217	24
Benzoic acid	2.585	1.041	70.29 ^a	69.72 69.413	23

Table-1 (contd.)

Hexahydrobenzoic acid	3.531	1.117	80.28 ^a 83.1	91.484	75.182	12
Salicylic acid	2.725	1.109	75.98 ^a 75.41	72.944	74.583	26 28
m-Hydroxybenzoic acid	2.718	1.109	74.54 ^a 74.52 ^a	72.784	74.583	26 28
p-Hydroxybenzoic acid	2.718	1.109	73.92 ^a 73.53	72.784	74.583	26
o-Toluic acid	3.002	1.195	84.32 80.83 ^a	79.277	81.026	29
m-Toluic acid	2.995	1.195	82.99 ^a 82.73	78.277	81.026	26 27
p-Toluic acid	2.995	1.195	82.49 ^a 80.73	79.162	81.026	23 30
Phenylacetic acid	3.041	1.195	82.10 82.72 ^a	80.199	81.026	23 30
o-Nitrobenzoic acid	3.089	1.239	76.1	81.327	84.323	32
m-Nitrobenzoic acid	3.082	1.239	80.22	81.166	84.323	34
p-Nitrotoluic acid	3.082	1.239	77.86	81.166	84.323	35
Quinolinic acid	3.039	1.241	72.3	80.176	84.473	35
Anthranilic acid	2.79	1.14	77.18	74.441	76.905	29
Cinnamic acid	3.244	1.307	79.0 ^a 78.36	84.805	89.417	31 31

^aExperimental values (if more than one) are the ones that are used for regression analysis. The resulting theoretical and experimental values of diamagnetic susceptibility are expressed in terms of 10^{-6} cgs unit or 4×10^{-9} SI unit.

(5) and (6) are found very close to the experimental values. These equations can be used to predict the diamagnetic susceptibility of any carboxylic acid by simply calculating ${}^1\chi_v$ or V_w .

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